

Demanding versus asking in Persian: Requestives as acts of verbal harassment

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Assuming that demanding and asking are different types of requestives, the study hypothesized (a) that they differ in their degrees and types of indirectness in request head acts (HAs) and internal and/or external supportive discourse moves (ISMs/ESMs), (b) that this is informed by people's ethnic mindsets, psychic delusions, and/or intentional attempts at negotiating social power, and (c) that any miscalculation of one's true social power may change a 'requestive' into an act of verbal 'harassment' that can terminate interlocutors' relationships and connections. To test these hypotheses, 229 'hurting' requests collected through verbal recalls, written recalls, and online interviews were coded by two expert human coders using Blum-Kulka, Færch and Kasper's (1989) coding scheme for HAs, and House and Kasper's (1981) and Færch and Kasper's (1989) coding schemes for ISMs and ESMs. Results indicated that hearers and speakers differ in their computations of requestives based on their ethnic, linguistic, and psychological perceptions.

Keywords: Asking; Demanding; Persian; Politeness; Requestive Speech Acts; Requestive Strategies

1. Introduction

Ever since Brown and Levinson (1987) disseminated their seminal work on politeness which relied heavily on the concept of indirectness and the sociolinguistic notions of face and facework, a good number of researchers from around the world have implemented the politeness theory in their investigations of speech acts in different languages. Politeness has more recently been approached from Sperber and Wilson's (1986, 1995, 2002) relevance-theoretic, Mey's (2001) socio-cultural interactional, and Kecskes' (2013) dialectical socio-cognitive perspectives, but studies conducted from the traditional Gricean (1957) perspective are still fashionable and continue to return considerable results (cf., Allan & Salmani Nodoushan, 2015). One speech act that has been investigated in a range of different languages is the requestive speech act (e.g., Alfattah & Ravindranath, 2009; Blum-Kulka,

House, & Kasper, 1989; Færch & Kasper, 1989; Lee, 2011; Marquez Reiter, 2000; Mendez Vallejo, 2013; Safont, 2005; Salmani Nodoushan, 2007, 2008; Salmani Nodoushan & Allami, 2011; Sifianou, 1999; Trosborg, 1995). Nevertheless, the problem is that scholars from around the world have treated all forms of this speech act in the same way. Since intentionality is at the heart of any speech act, it is hypothesized that ‘demanding’ with ‘asking’—two major sub-types of requestives—must differ in terms of requesting strategies since they are suitable for different intentions. To my knowledge, no study has yet sought to compare ‘demanding’ with ‘asking’ in Persian to see if interlocutors’ use the same or different requesting strategies in both, and if not, what their intentions might be. As such, the current study compares asking and demanding in Persian and tries to show that, in spite of their being requestives from a Gricean-pragmatic perspective, they differ in fundamental ways from a politeness angle.

2. background

In a purely linguistic sense, ‘what is said’ is what is said, but when it comes to pragmatics, and even more so to politeness, what is said is what is communicated—i.e., what is said plus what is intended, implied, or left unsaid to be discovered by the hearer. This is how a sentence is differentiated from an utterance. Semantics is all about meaning, but pragmatics is all about intentionality. The founding figure who is often credited with the conception of ‘utterance’ meaning is Grice (1957). Before Grice, meaning was formal (i.e., confined within ‘forms’ in a Chomskyan sense) because ‘meaning that *p*’ was tantamount to ‘it is the fact that *p*’. Ever since Grice’s conception of ‘set of pragmatic maxims’, meaning has become and continues to be ‘informal’ in the sense that “‘A meant something by *x*’ is roughly equivalent to ‘A uttered *x* with the intention of inducing a belief by means of the recognition of this intention’” (Grice, 1957, p. 219).

No sooner had Grice unveiled his ‘informal’ meaning than ‘informal’ linguistics (i.e., pragmatics) started (as a parallel to the Chomskyan notion of ‘formal’ linguistics); however, pragmatics remained the Cinderella of semiotics, looked down upon by her step-sisters, ‘semantics’ and ‘syntactics’, until around the 1980s. Austin (1962), for instance, envisaged a set of performatives, also called communicative acts, that could communicate intentions (See also Bach & Harnish, 1979). The name performative was chosen because almost all utterances, à la Austin, can partake of the nature of actions (Salmani Nodoushan, 1995, 2006, 2014, 2019b; see also Rath Foley & Karlsson, 2021). Likewise, Strawson (1964) used the ‘conventional’ vs. ‘nonconventional’ classificatory principle to propose ‘noninstitutional’ and ‘institutional’ acts, the former being mainly Gricean in nature, the latter ‘ritualistic’ (Salmani Nodoushan, 2013, 2016a); Bach and Harnish (1979)

brought Strawson's dichotomy to bear on their conception of a posteriori 'verdictive' and a priori 'effective' speech acts. Searle (1969) conceived 'felicity' conditions (in the form of essential, sincerity, preparatory, and propositional content rules) which he considered necessary for the realization of speech acts. He also improved Austin's classification of speech acts to include assertives, directives, expressives, declaratives, and commissives (Searle, 1979; see also Leech, 1983; Leech & Thomas, 1985).

It was not until the 1980s when pragmatics began to gather momentum. A spectrum of approaches to Gricean maxims (together referred to as the 'component perspective') emerged (Salmani Nodoushan, 2017); at one end of the spectrum stood Horn's (1984, 1988, 2007) neo-Gricean Q-principle and R-principle, which aim to minimize hearers' processing and speakers' production efforts, respectively. Somewhere around the middle of the spectrum stood Levinson's (1987, 1995, 2000) three heuristics—i.e., Horn's Q-principle scaffolded with Levinson's own I-principle and M-principle. At the other end of the spectrum stood Sperber and Wilson's (1986, 1995, 2002) relevance theory (RT) with its only principle for both communication and cognition instead of all of the Gricean maxims. Pragmatics developed even further in the 21st century with Mey's (2001) socio-cultural interactional and Kecskes' (2013) dialectical socio-cognitive perspectives, but a discussion of these topics is beyond the scope of the current paper (See Salmani Nodoushan, 2017).

As a neo-Gricean theory in spirit, politeness appeared in 1987 when Brown and Levinson dovetailed Gricean pragmatics and Goffman's (1955, 1959) theory of facework (Salmani Nodoushan, 2012, 2019a); facework comprises face and line. Face, à la Goffman, is the positive image of themselves that people project or the good impression of themselves that they try to create in social settings (including speech situations and events). Line consists of whatever they do to achieve that end. Taken together, face and line turn up into facework (Goffman, 1959; see also Salmani Nodoushan, 1995, 2019a, 2019b). How the general public evaluates face is called the emic or first-order view of face, but how a scientist evaluates it is called the etic or second-order view of face (Haugh, 2007; Salmani Nodoushan, 2019b; Sifianou, 2011; Terkourafi, 2007, 2011).

Dovetailing facework and Gricean pragmatic notions (i.e., maxims, principles, and felicity conditions) allowed Brown and Levinson (1987) to fabricate and promulgate their 'etic' politeness theory. They built their theory on the assumption that individuals (i.e., both hearers and speakers) have positive and negative face needs, the former being defined in terms of the desire to be liked and to be free (i.e., freedom of action), and the latter in terms of the desire not to be imposed on (i.e., freedom from imposition) (cf., Salmani

Nodoushan 2007, 2008, 2012, 2014, 2019a). Face can be lost, maintained, or enhanced, and ‘face wants’—i.e., face needs—are emotional/psychological in nature.

As such, (a) face wants/needs and (b) facework are the two pedestals upon which Brown and Levinson’s etic theory of politeness stands. They take a radical position in relation to politeness and argue that conversation is more about the negotiation and redress of face through positive and/or negative politeness than the exchange of information. Any utterance, à la Brown and Levinson, is potentially threatening to either the positive or the negative face of both the speaker and the hearer; hence, face-threatening acts (FTAs). Both parties in a conversation have five options by means of which they can ‘save’ or ‘lose’ face in social interactions: (a) bald performance of FTAs without positive or negative politeness, (b) performance of FTAs with positive politeness (through a show of interest), (c) performance of FTAs with negative politeness (through a show of deference), (d) performance of FTAs with off-record, vague strategies of indirectness, or (e) avoiding the performance of FTAs altogether (cf., Brown & Levinson, 1987, pp. 103-210).

In this connection, Brown and Levinson (1987) argued that the degree to which interlocutors decide to mitigate their performance of FTAs depends on the distribution of face among them and is a function of three factors: (1) relative power, (2) social distance, and (3) the weightiness of imposition (i.e., P, D, and R, respectively). Later, Fraser (1990) and Spencer-Oatey (1996) criticized these variables, and Scollon and Scollon (2001) reformulated them in terms of three politeness systems based on levels of Perceived Situational Seriousness (PSS) with three factors: (a) hierarchy, (b) deference, and (c) solidarity, depending on the presence or absence of power and/or distance:

Perceived Situational Seriousness (PSS)	Power	Distance
Hierarchical Politeness System (HPS)	+	+
Deferential Politeness System (DPS)	-	+
Solidarity Politeness System (SPS)	-	-

Brown and Levinson’s (1987) politeness theory spurred an outburst of interest in politeness research across different languages, and many scholars from around the world conducted politeness studies focused on specific speech acts. One speech act that has been researched in a range of languages is the speech act of requesting—or ‘requestive’ speech act (RSA hereafter). In their formulation of the discursive structure of RSAs, politeness researchers found that each requestive includes an obligatory Head Act (HA) which may be accompanied by internal and external supportive discourse moves (or ISM versus ESM); ISMs appear inside the HA sentence/utterance (often in the form of lexical and syntactic modifications), but ESMs appear in separate

collocative utterances pre-posed or post-posed to the HA utterance (Blum-Kulka, Færch, & Kasper, 1989; House & Kasper, 1981; Salmani Nodoushan 2007, 2008; Salmani Nodoushan & Allami, 2011—See also Marquez Reiter, 2000; Safont, 2005; Sifianou, 1999; Trosborg, 1995). In essence, ISMs and ESMs are communicative conventions behind utterances that scaffold HAs to make sure what (Thomas, 1983) categorized as ‘pragmalinguistic failure’ and ‘sociopragmatic failure’ cannot and will not happen (cf., Salmani Nodoushan, 1995; Wolfson, 1989;).

3. Method

3.1. Context of the study

Requestives are defined as ‘directives’ of which (a) the job is to elicit some information, or to bring about some effect, through the hearer’s course of action; and (b) the performance will satisfy the speaker’s wants and needs (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007, 2008; cf., Félix-Brasdefer, 2005). Some requests are like highly flammable explosives that can explode an entire relationship due to their great potential for imposition (especially when their completion requires that requestees invest their money, property, time, or whatever they consider highly precious); as such, requests should be handled with maximum care (i.e., scaffolded with appropriate ESMs and ISMs)—specifically in intra-cultural settings where both sides of an interaction are native speakers of the same mother tongue and belong in the same social and ethnic milieu. Speakers need to know how to phrase and deliver their requests so that hearers will interpret them as requests rather than, for instance, as a discursive act of harassment. Very often misunderstandings arise from interactants’ differences in (a) evaluating the size of imposition of a speech act, (b) perceiving the seriousness of the speech situation/event in connection to their own relative powers and/or true social distance, and (c) their value judgments (Hymes, 1972; Salmani Nodoushan, 1995; Thomas, 1983).

As such, the use or non-use of ESMs and ISMs in requestives in social and interpersonal speech events can function as face-saving or face-threatening moves that can aggravate or mitigate the force of HAs (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007, 2008), and this is the very factor on which the main hypotheses of the current study are based: (a) that demanding and asking, although grouped under the umbrella term ‘requests’, differ in their degrees and/or types of mitigation; (b) that this is informed by people’s pragmatic mindsets, psychic delusions, and/or intentional attempts at the negotiation of power; and (c) that any miscalculation of one’s true social power may change a ‘requestive’ into an act of verbal ‘harassment’ that can terminate interlocutors’ relationships and connections.

3.2. Analysis framework

The framework used for the analysis of the data of this study is a comprehensive framework driven, on the one hand, from Blum-Kulka et al.'s (1989) coding scheme for HAs, and on the other hand from House and Kasper's (1981), and Færch and Kasper's (1989) coding schemes for ISMs and ESMs. Blum-Kulka et al. (1989) used a three-fold coding system to identify levels of indirectness in request HAs: (1) Direct Strategies (DS), (2) Conventionally Indirect Strategies (CIS), and (3) Nonconventionally Indirect Strategies (NIS):

1. Direct Strategies (DS)

- a) Mood Derivable (assessing hearer's readiness/reluctance to accept the request)
- b) Performative (requesting directly)
- c) Obligation (telling hearers about their obligations and duties)
- d) Need Statement (telling hearers about one's need for help, favor, etc.)
- e) Want Statement (telling hearers that one wants them to perform the act)

2. Conventionally Indirect Strategies (CIS)

- a) Suggestory Formulae (making a suggestion to be computed as a request)
- b) Query Preparatory (querying hearers about their readiness/willingness to accept the request)

3. Nonconventionally Indirect Strategies (NIS)

- a) Mild Hint (beating about the bush by providing quite indirect hints which signal a request)
- b) Strong Hint (beating about the bush by providing very strong hints which signal a request)

Likewise, House and Kasper (1981) and Færch and Kasper (1989) used coding schemes informed by the discursive strategies which speakers use to scaffold HAs internally and/or externally:

1. Internal Supportive Moves (i.e., modifications in HAs)

- a) Lexical ISMs (e.g., mitigators, mental verbs, hedging, etc.)
- b) Syntactic ISMs (e.g., conditionals, questions, etc.)

2. External Supportive Moves (i.e., modifications pre- or post-posed to HAs)

- a) Providing reasons (as to why the request is being made)
- b) Using preparators (to get the hearer ready for the HA)
- c) Using disarmers (to persuade the hearer to accept the HA)
- d) Using precursors/alerters (to signal the HA)
- e) Suggesting alternatives (to allow options for the hearer)
- f) Using positive politeness strategies (e.g., praising, flattering, etc.)

3.3. Participants

A call for participation in this study was sent to 842 people who are on the researcher's *Whatsapp* contact list. Of these people, 271 individuals ($N=271$) expressed their willingness to participate in the study. They were assured that their identities will remain confidential. All of them were asked to provide their demographic details for the study. Table 1 displays the composition of the participants in this study.

Table 1
Participants Demographic Details

Age				Education				Gender		
20-30	31-40	41-50	51+	PhD	MA	BA	other	M	F	Other
94	119	37	21	47	64	133	27	114	149	8

All of these participants were 'requestees'. They were the interactants towards whom requests had been extended by friends, strangers, or more socially-powerful requesters.

3.4. Procedure and corpus

For this study, two sets of data were needed: (1) samples of 'hurting' requests, and (2) detailed information about requesters' linguistic, cultural, and social backgrounds as well as their demography and personality. For this study, 'hurting' requests were operationally defined as (1) cases where speakers are expected to 'ask' for an action or some information, but they choose to 'demand' as if they are entitled to receive the service/information, or (2) cases where requests are delivered with inappropriate HAs, ISMs, and/or ESMs. For the first data set, each participant was asked to recall three 'hurting' requests extended towards them, one by a friend, one by a stranger, and one by an apparently or truly socially-more-powerful person (i.e., solidarity, deference, and power categories, respectively). They were asked to recall and reproduce the exact wordings of those requests as closely and precisely as they could. For the second data set, each participant was asked to answer the following questions (in relation to each request):

- 1) Why did you feel hurt or harassed by the request? What was wrong in the requester's act?
- 2) Why do you think the requester behaved that way? What specific reasons do you think they had for their specific way of handling the request? Do you think they had any specific reasons that justified their behavior?

- 3) If you wanted to rate the emotional pain that you felt on a scale from zero (i.e., no pain) to ten (i.e., 100% pain), where would this request stand?
- 4) How should the requester have phrased their request to avoid hurting your emotions?
- 5) What is your evaluation of the economic, cultural, social, linguistic, and ethnic backgrounds as well as the personality of the requester? How would you describe their personality and character?

The participants in the study were assured that the totality of the collected data will remain confidential, will only be used for the current study, and will be disposed immediately after the study.

For purposes of data collection, the participants had three options from which they could choose:

- (1) to write the requests in the form of written recalls and answer the follow-up questions in written form;
- (2) to record the requests and their answers to the questions in the form of voice memos; or
- (3) to participate in private online structured interviews with the researcher to provide the requests and the answers.

These options served two purposes: (a) participants' convenience, and (b) data triangulation. Notwithstanding the widely-accepted belief that real-life observation is the most authentic and reliable way of data collection in sociolinguistic and anthropological research (Beebe & Cummings, 1996; Blum-Kulka et al., 1989; Cohen & Olshtain, 1994; Olshtain & Blum-Kulka, 1985; Rintell & Mitchell, 1989; Wolfson & Manes, 1980;), it is not practical in the majority of small-scale studies like this one. Moreover, there are always concerns about observer paradox (Labov, 1972), Hawthorne effect (Cox, 2000; Salmani Nodoushan, 2016a), and horns and halo effects (Burton, Cook, Howlett, & Newman, 2015) in any real-life observations. An alternative is to 'triangulate' different sources of data (Aijmer, 1996; Félix-Brasdefer, 2010; Grainger & Mills, 2016; Olshtain & Blum-Kulka, 1985), and this was done in the current study—through (1) written recalls, (2) verbal recalls, and (3) online structured interviews. Moreover, giving the participants the option to choose the method with which they were more convenient would also result in more accurate data.

In this way, 86 participants preferred online interviews, 111 chose to provide the researcher with written recalls and answers, and 74 recoded their voice memos. As such, 271 instances of 'hurting' requests for each politeness system (i.e., solidarity, deference, and power) were collected. The participants were asked to recall only those instances of requests extended towards them

that had hurt their emotions because the main aim of this study was to find cases where requesters are expected to 'ask' but feel entitled to 'demand', or cases where requestees misinterpret 'asking' as 'demanding'. It should be emphasized that not all of the 271 instances of hurting request in each category were analyzed; it was decided that only those instances which were highly hurting be analyzed. As such, only those requests in each category that had received a rating of 7 and above on the emotional-pain scale were selected for analysis. After the application of this criterion, a total of 229 highly hurting requests (73 from solidarity, 54 from deference, and 102 from power categories, respectively) were retained, and the rest were discarded.

For purposes of data analysis, it would be both possible and practical to submit the collected written recalls and the transcripts of interviews and voice memos to computer software packages (such as *MAXQDA*), to conduct 'inductive content analyses' which would enable the researcher to (a) perform bottom-up codings, (b) identify themes, and (b) draw empirical conclusions. However, computer software packages are highly mechanical, and may not do justice to the data extracted from human speech behavior. As such, it was decided that the whole of the refined data set (i.e., the 229 highly hurting requests) be coded by two expert human coders. In the first phase of coding, each expert coded the data separately; in the second phase, they met to discuss their codings, and resolve any probable mismatch. Inter-coder correlations showed that the codings were reliable ($\alpha=0.94$ for request codings, and $\alpha=0.89$ for follow-up questions).

For purposes of coding the obtained requests, the human coders used the above-mentioned comprehensive framework which merged Blum-Kulka et al.'s (1989) coding scheme for HAs, and House and Kasper's (1981), and Færch and Kasper's (1989) coding schemes for ISMs and ESMs. In addition to this framework, the participants' answers to the follow-up questions were also analyzed, through an inductive content analysis, for recurrent and/or related patterns which could be grouped into general themes that would explain the reasons why the requesters had phrased their requests the way they had.

4. Results

As stated before, a professional's scientific perspective (called the etic or second-order perspective) is different from that of the general public. The first set of results were obtained from an etic perspective using the merged Blum-Kulka et al.'s (1989) coding scheme for HAs, and House and Kasper's (1981), and Færch and Kasper's (1989) coding schemes for ISMs and ESMs. Table 2 (below) displays the results.

Table 2
Results Obtained from an Etic Perspective (Frequencies)

		SPS	DPS	HPS
HAs:	1. Direct Strategies (DS)	58	23	102
	a) Mood Derivable	0	0	0
	b) Performative	29	17	93
	c) Obligation	18	0	0
	d) Need Statement	0	0	0
	e) Want Statement	11	6	9
	2. Conventionally Indirect Strategies (CIS)	15	31	0
	a) Suggestory Formulae	0	0	0
	b) Query Preparatory	15	31	0
	3. Nonconventionally Indirect Strategies (NIS)	0	0	0
a) Mild Hint	0	0	0	
b) Strong Hint	0	0	0	
ISM/ESMs:	1. Internal Supportive Moves	0	37	0
	a) Lexical ISMs	0	37	0
	b) Syntactic ISMs	0	0	0
	2. External Supportive Moves	0	0	7
	a) Reasons	0	0	7
	b) Preparators	0	0	0
	c) Disarmers	9	0	0
	d) Precursors/Alerters	0	0	0
	e) Alternatives	0	0	0
	f) Politeness strategies	0	0	0

Demanding where the requester is normally expected to 'ask' is considered inappropriate and impolite since the requester wrongly feels entitled to demand, and takes the acceptance of their demand for granted. Such acts hurt the requestees emotionally; hence, hurting requests (i.e., unjustified and inappropriately-phrased demands). As Table 2 shows, NISs (i.e., mild or strong hints) were not used in the head acts of hurting requests. CISs were not used in power (or hierarchy) politeness systems either. While performatives (in the form of direct imperatives) were the preferred HA structure in solidarity and power systems, queries were preferred in the deference system, but these queries were not preparatory; that is, they began with inappropriate phrases (e.g., do, where, etc.) rather than with phrases that appropriately and politely signal a request (e.g., would you please, would you mind, etc.). Want statements and phrases signaling obligation were also found in the HAs, but they were considered inappropriate because the requesters were not in the right position to use them; rather, their use was

based on the requesters' miscomputation of their own power and the requestees' obligations.

Table 3

Summary of the Themes Found through Inductive Content Analysis of Participants' Answers to Follow-up Questions

	SPS	DPS	HPS
Q1	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Violation of privacy • Size of imposition • Inappropriate phrasing 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Illegal interference • Exploitation • Violation of privacy • Delivering with wrong T-V address form • Using swearwords • DS instead of CIS/NCIS 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bullying • Threatening • Exploiting • Abuse of power • Violation of ethical codes
Q2	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Fatuity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Ideological dogma • Condescendence • Rascality • Fatuity 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • System corruption • Weakness of law • Character frailty
Q4	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shouldn't have demanded 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shouldn't have demanded • Should have asked, not demanded • Should have made it indirect and polite 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Shouldn't have demanded
Q5	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Exploiter • Fatuitous • Abuser 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Rascal • Fatuitous • Presumptuous/Condescending 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Delusion of grandeur • Miscomputation of power • Abuser of power • Immorality
e.g.,	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demanding a loan • Demanding car for weeks of travel • Demanding valid surety • Demanding villa in north for some weeks • Demanding translation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demanding observation of ideological dressing codes • Demanding turn in a queue • Demanding task performance • Using swearwords • Using offensive address forms 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Demanding graft/quota publication space • Demanding graft co-authorship • Demanding bribe

ISMs were not found in the power and solidarity systems, but requesters in the deference system used lexical ISMs; Persian is a language with T-V

distinction (i.e., 'tu' versus 'vos'), but T should not be used in the deference system since strangers are not considered close enough to be allowed to use this address form (Salmani Nodoushan, 2006). However, T was found in 37 cases, and this is clearly inappropriate and offensive.

The deference system had not used any ESMs, but the solidarity system had used disarmers in nine demands; likewise, the power system had used reasons in seven demands. Polite disarmers are in the form praise, compliments, flattering, etc., but the disarmers that had been used in the demands analyzed in this study were of a different kind; they had been phrased in such a way as to corner the requestee to make sure that the requestee would not find any way to opt out and decline the request (e.g., HA+ a phrase that would mean 'and I won't take no as an answer'). Reasons had been used in seven requests in the power system, but they had been used in such a way as to give the requestees a guilt trip (e.g., HA+I passed you in the course, but you didn't deserve it.).

These results, when compared to previous studies on Persian requests (Salmani Nodoushan, 2007, 2008; Salmani Nodoushan & Allami, 2011), show a radical difference. Previous studies showed that requesters had made use of a lot of ISMs and ESMs in requests, and the HAs had mainly been NISs or sometimes CISs, in both cases scaffolded by ISMs and ESMs, but the findings of the current study tell us a different story. To explain why this has happened, we need to evaluate the answers that the participants of this study have given to the follow-up question from their 'emic' perspectives.

The recurrent patterns (which could be labeled and grouped into general themes) were elicited through inductive content analysis conducted by the two expert human coders. Table 3 (above) summarizes the results. Question 3 is not included in the table since it was used as a gauge to screen and select the 229 requests that were analyzed.

5. Discussion

Table 3 (above) is quite revealing and shows that requesters' demands in solidarity and power systems, and in most cases in the deference system, had not been warranted, and should not have been made in the first place. This clearly shows that speakers are likely to make demands on the basis of wrong/unwarranted assumptions. Deliberate avoidance of performing ISMs and/or ESMs, and failure to correctly perceive the seriousness of the conversational situation can have dire consequences for the requester. Such miscalculations are likely to happen due to the delicate interaction between 'salience', 'context', and 'common ground', the three big factors that partly control interpersonal interactions (cf., Kecskes, 2008, 2013; Kecskes & Zhang, 2009).

Based on the inductive content analysis performed on the participants' responses to the follow-up questions, it was found that in the solidarity system, 'size of imposition' and 'violation of privacy' accounted for the majority of impolite demands (57.53% and 35.61%, respectively). Only 6.86% of the cases were hurting due to their inappropriate phrasing. When asked to provide possible reasons that could explain the requesters' unwarranted demands, the requestees picked out only one weakness in their friends' character: fatuity. A fatuitous person is one who is complacently stupid and does not know what is socially right or wrong. From an etic perspective, it seems that 'miscomputation of the depth of friendship' may be one factor than can explain why misunderstandings have happened in the solidarity system. Notwithstanding what was said before, the requestees should—ironically—be asked why they continue to befriend people whom they evaluate as fatuitous; their answer would most probably be, "You ask really hard questions!".

In the power system, requests were computed as 'hurting demands' in cases where requesters abused their power (18.62%), or the requestees felt that they had been (1) picked on (7.85%), (2) exploited (13.72%), (3) indirectly threatened of dire consequences if they declined the hurting requests (21.57%), or (4) forced to violate ethical codes (38.24%). Bullying, threatening, and abuse of power involved cases where police officers and office cadre demanded bribe. Exploitation and violation of ethical codes involved university professors who demanded (without any material contribution) that their names appear as 'graft' co-authors in their former graduate students' forthcoming publications, or demanded that journal editors violate their codes of conduct to allow 'graft' and 'quota' publication space for the publication of the professors' plagiarized, weak, or grafted manuscripts. When asked to provide their emic evaluation of the economic, cultural, social, linguistic, and ethnic backgrounds as well as the personality of the requesters, the participants of the study identified 'delusions of grandeur', 'miscomputation of power', 'abuser of power' and 'immorality' as the possible drives behind the requesters' unwarranted demands. This shows that people may have certain misconceptions about their 'selves' and what they are entitled to, and that this character frailty is likely to make them violate politeness and pragmatic maxims in contexts where they should not. One "fake" professor of applied linguistics from a major state university in Tehran was specifically identified by 19 participants in the study who described him as an excessively-conceited and absorbed-in-oneself person who has a "long and painful history of giving his former graduate students frequent guilt trips when demanding, due to his own delusion of grandeur and corrupt family" (Respondent #33).

The requestees' reaction to the demands in the deference system was somewhat different. While they all emphasized that the demands should not have been made in the solidarity and power systems, they admitted that some of the demands in the deference system could have been warranted if they had been phrased appropriately to look like 'asking', but not 'demanding'. Extending a 'demand' where you are expected to 'ask' is offensive and abusive, but this may be due to cultural differences among the different ethnic groups that live in Iran. The cases that comprised situations where the demand should not have been extended in the first place, according to the requestees, included interference into personal territory which was not allowed by law (12.97%) and violation of privacy (5.56%). An example of the former is a pseudo-religious man's demanding a young lady to observe the ideological dressing code that he thinks is right. An example of the latter is a cab driver from the 'Lur' ethnicity who is working in Tehran and in one occasion stops by a bakery, gives a passenger in the cab some cash, and tells him, "go buy some loaves of bread for me."

Cases where asking was allowed, but demanding was not, included 'delivering the request with inappropriate T-V forms of address (29.62%), 'using swearwords in the demanding query' (22.22%), and 'using DS HAs instead of CIS/NCIS HAs' (22.22%). Using Direct Strategies (DS) in HAs in the deference system is not allowed in Persian—unless there is an emergency (like 'Look out!') to alert the addressee of a life-threatening danger. If used in other cases, such HAs are interpreted as demands, and the requester is taken for an impolite individual who feels entitled to demand where he is culturally obliged to ask. In the samples analyzed, the requesters belonged in two categories: (a) the elderly, and (b) people from Hamadan and Kermanshah (two provinces in the west of Iran). Seniority (in terms of age) is a factor that gives the elderly the assumption that they have to be respected and obeyed, but the new generation is no longer behaving in traditional ways, and the generation gap disallows the younger generation living in the modern era to be addressed through DS HAs; the younger generation takes it for granted that the elderly are obliged to respect all people regardless of their age, but the elderly assume that younger generations are culturally obliged to obey them. This creates complications. Likewise, using T instead of V as address forms was observed in only the requests that had been made by Bushehri requesters; Bushehr is a province located in the south of Iran, and the dialect spoken in that region lacks the T-V distinction whereas the Persian spoken in other parts of Iran makes this distinction. In requests in the deference system, the polite form is to use the V pronoun (i.e., plural you), but in the analyzed sample, Bushehri requesters had used the T pronoun (i.e., singular you). This supports Kecskes' (2013) concerns about the big three factors (i.e., context, common ground, and salience). It also shows that cultural differences among

ethnic groups can be costly in the deference system. Finally, swearwords were found in the requests that had been made by Isfahani and Bandar Abbasi requesters. These comprised queries, not in the preparatory form, but in the simple question form (e.g., beginning with 'which way is . . .' instead of 'would you please tell me which way . . . is?'), which started with swearwords as mitigators instead of the appropriate form 'please' (e.g., *Xare Azadi kodum vare?* Trans: You donkey, which way is the Azadi Square?). 'Xare' (you donkey) is a swearword in Persian, but it is used for social swearing and endearment in Isfahani dialect, and so is 'ʔæy yæru' (hey you) in Bandar Abbasi dialect. This supports previous studies that have shown ethnic, dialectal, and cultural differences in Iran are corrosive to politeness (Salmani Nodoushan, 2016b).

6. Conclusion

All in all, the data analyzed in this study showed that ISMs and ESMs are absent in the majority of requests that are labeled as emotionally-hurting and impolite by requestees. When people avoid mitigating the force and/or directness of their requests, (1) their acts are computed as offensive 'demands' instead of 'acts of asking', (2) impoliteness is inevitable, and (3) social ties are in danger. It was also concluded that people's pragmatic mindsets (i.e., cultural, personal, and relevance-theoretic computations of context, common ground, and salience), psychic delusions, and/or intentional attempts at negotiation of power drive(s) them to 'demand' rather than 'ask'. In the power system, too, people's miscalculation of their power and delusions of grandeur may mutate their requestive acts into acts of harassment that are likely to terminate their social ties with their requestees.

The study showed that, although the hearers had felt that the requests were impolite from their own emic perspectives, the speakers had felt that they had the right to make the requests in the way they actually had, due to their socio-cultural backgrounds, linguistic backgrounds, misconception of social power, and so forth. It should be emphasized, once again, that politeness is mainly a sociolinguistic phenomenon and cannot be approached from a purely Gricean linguistic perspective. The classification of speech acts in linguistics or philosophy does not comply with their categorization in sociolinguistics or politeness theory.

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